

Stig2Health: Stigma-directed services to improve ‘linkage to care’ for people living with HIV in rural Tanzania: study protocol for a nested pre-post implementation study within the Kilombero and Ulanga Antiretroviral Cohort

Table S1: Outline group support therapy and group health education

Group Support Therapy (1-3)	Group Health Education (1-3)
<p>Session 1: Integration of HIV and ART in everyday life</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Challenges of adherence including taking drugs, storage, picking up refills and being away from home (4). - Possible integration strategies. A practical approach. 	<p>HIV Background, Progression and Adherence</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Definition of and differences between HIV and AIDS. - Symptoms. - Progression of HIV in the body including entry, window period, disease. - Adherence.
<p>Session 2 Internalized stigma</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Idea of internalized stigma (5, 6). - Self-blame and regret (7). - Personal empowerment (5, 8). 	<p>HIV Transmission and Prevention of HIV Infection</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - HIV Transmission. Impossible means of transmission from hearsay in the community. - Risky behaviors and methods of risk reduction.
<p>Session 3 Depression and Coping</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mentalization. - Depression and HIV including symptoms, red flags, support system (9-11). - Positive and negative coping strategies (8, 9, 12). 	<p>Antiretroviral Therapy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - HIV treatment. Adherence. - Side effects. Drug interaction. Drug resistance. - Possibilities to maximize adherence and treatment success.
<p>Session 4 Disclosure and relationship</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Non-Disclosure (13). - Disclosure and communication (9). - Relationship. - Family planning. 	<p>Mother to Child transmission</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MTCT Risk reduction (Antenatal, labor, delivery). - Breast feeding and alternatives. - Safer Sex Rules, importance of disclosing to a partner. - Family planning.
<p>Session 5 Community stigma</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Definition and situations of community stigma (13). - Perceived and Enacted Stigma. - Social support and being a part of the community (14). 	<p>HIV and Lifestyle</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - HIV and nutrition. Balanced diet. - Alternative healing practices and associated risk. - Prevention of sexual transmitted diseases. - Tuberculosis and HIV, symptoms, prevent transmission. - Medical support during therapy.

Group support therapy and group health education are based on participant-centered learning (2), social support (15), strength-based non-judgmental communication (16), identifying communalities (17), creating hope (18) and active listening (11). Each session consists of an introduction including group therapy rules, a possibility to share problems (10, 18) and combines peer group support therapy with group health education (9). We use active learning techniques like role play, brainstorming, discussions with active listening (11), storytelling and exercises with picture cards (2).

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